

The Stock Market and Economic Growth

Dipak Bahadur Bhandari, Ph.D.¹

Abstract

This paper investigates the causal relationship between stock market development and economic growth of Nepal for the period 1981-2012 using a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). The purpose of this paper is to examine the long-run relationship between these variables, applying the Johansen co-integration analysis based on the classical unit roots tests. In assessing the link between the new measures and financial development and growth, the results support the existence of an overall positive relationship. The econometric test results suggest that stock market development in the Nepal has a positive impact in the long run.

INTRODUCTION

The stock market is a component of financial system. It play role to transfer the financial surplus and it can be classified into two levels. First is primary market and another is **secondary market**. Primary market as a form of the stock market will bridge with investment banks and businesses entrepreneur person who are looking to increased additional capital by selling ordinary shares, preference shares as well different kinds of bonds (Shrestha and Bhandari, 2010). This process involves the business being 'listed' on the Stock Exchange or 'floating'. In this case, the business will effectively get its capital through the initial sale of its shares. Allen (1992, p.92) elaborated on this perspective by describing what he calls the 'checking role of the stock market'.

In the primary market, initial public offerings (IPOs) are a platform where due to multiple checking by investors resources are allocated to viable firms. That is aggregate information acquired by investors' offers a means of ample information asymmetries between firms and fund providers. The intensive for investor in acquire information comes from the under pricing typically associated with IPOs. Allen (1992) posits further that once the firm is in the stock market, it need not be checked extensively by the markets, provided it is generating reasonable earnings. If the firm is not generating sufficient earnings (or has a high earnings pay-out policy) and has to resort to further outside equity, then the same information acquisition process described for IPOs applies. In other words, IPOs and repeat fund

¹ Dr. Bhandari is Associate Professor at School of Business, Pokhara University

solicitations stimulate more intensive information collection and checking by investors, but once the firm is in the market, the monitoring and control impetus shifts to other market mechanisms such as the market for corporate control and market based managerial incentives, in addition to the 'built-in incentive for investors to assess what the management is doing' (Allen, 1992 p.100).

The second form of stock market is secondary market. In the secondary stock market are traded for the existing securities. Thus, the stock exchange market work effectively for those people who want to sell securities in touch with those who are looking to buy securities is a market for second hand shares. In the stock exchange market mainly has two main 'players' for providing facilities to the savers and investors. They are stock brokers and market makers, Bhandari (2010). There are various authors about the stock market development has been the subject of intensive theoretical and empirical studies (see Demirguc-Kunt and Levine, 1995; and Levine and Zervos, 1993, 1995, 1998). In principle, a well-developed stock market should increase saving and efficiently allocate capital to productive investments, which leads to an increase in the rate of economic growth.

The stock markets also play roles to the mobilization of domestic savings through the set of financial instruments to savers to diversify their portfolios. Basically, stock market provides an important source of investment capital at relatively low cost. Stock markets provide the facilities for savers and investors to manage with liquidity risk by allowing those who are hit by a liquidity fright to sell their securities to other investors who do not suffer from a liquidity shock. As a result, capital is not removed from organization to meet short-term liquidity needs. In addition, another important function of stock markets is mobilization of capital to the corporate sector, and its impacts on aggregate production in the economy (Acharya and Pedersen, 2005).

Debt is the most important sources of financing for the firms; however it is unavailable in many countries, especially in developing countries, where bank loans may be limited to a selected group of

companies and individual investors. This limitation can also reflect constraints in credit markets arising from the possibility that a bank's return from lending to a specific group of borrowers does not increase as the interest rate it charges to borrowers rises (Stiglitz and Weiss, 1981 and Cho, 1986). A Active and developed stock markets alter the pattern of demand for money, and booming stock markets create liquidity, and hence spur economic growth (Arnoud, Boot, Gopalan and Thakor, 2008).

The stock market development is very important for the economic growth of nation. There are various empirical studies for stock market development and economic growth was supported, such as (Levine and Zervos, 1993; Atje and Jovanovic, 1993; Levine and Zervos, 1998). However, these studies focus the importance of stock market development in the growth process, they exclude examine financial intermediations and banking sector development and economic growth in a unified framework. On the other hand, (Rousseau and Wachtel, 2000; Beck and Levine, 2003; and Bekaert et al, 2005) showed that stock market development is correlated with growth rates of real GDP per capita. More importantly, they found that stock market liquidity and banking development both predict the future growth rate of economy when they both enter the growth regression. Nevertheless, these studies suffer from various statistical weaknesses.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A large body of empirical studies clearly shows that the relationship between stock markets and economic growth is strongly and positively correlated. This is a solid and uncontroversial result, and it appears to be true across time and for many countries. Indeed, the data confirm that as economies develop stock markets tend to expand both in terms of the number of listed companies and in terms of market capitalization, (Atje and Jovanovich, 1993; Demirgüç-Kunt and Levine, 1996a and 1996b; Demirguc-Kunt and Maksimovic, 1996; Korajczyk, 1996; Levine and Zervos, 1996 & 1998; and Arnold, Bassanini and Scarpetta, 2007). Explaining the role played by stock markets requires building in frictions such as informational or transaction costs into the theory. Different frictions motivate

different types of financial contracts, markets and institutions.

King and Levine (1993a) initiated growth studies with cross country data sets that have become the benchmark for other studies (Wachtel (2001)). According to Levine (1997), the link between stock market development and economic growth was first investigated more than forty years ago. Goldsmit (1969) used the value of financial intermediary assets divided by GNP to measure financial development. Using data for 35 countries over the period 1860 – 1963, when available, Goldsmit (1963, p.48) concluded that: “periods of more rapid economic growth have been accompanied, through not without exception, by an above-average rate of financial development.”

The functional approach of Levine (1997) provided a useful framework to think about the role of stock market development in economic growth. Stock markets perform certain financial functions in the economy. Each of these financial functions have important role in economic growth through two channels: capital accumulation and technological innovation.

During the recent year finance, economic, business as well as econometric research has found quantitative evidence documenting the link between stock market development and economic growth. In term of estimation approaches these studied are divided into three categories: cross country, panel studies and time series studies, Bhandari, (2010).

The model by Saint-Paul (1992) emphasised the role of stock markets in the choice of methodology. It posits that there is a strategic complementarity between financial markets and technology, such that in the absence of financial markets firms will choose technologies that are more flexible, less risky but also less productive, as a means of managing risk. Given this scenario, there is in turn no incentive to develop financial markets. However, where financial markets are developed, technology will tend to be more specialised, risky and more productive, thereby aiding growth, and further entrenching the need for financial markets. Stock markets facilitate such improved division of labour

and technological specialisation by permitting agents to hedge via holding a diversified portfolio. Thus, this model emphasises the possible mutually reinforcing interaction between finance, technology and growth.

Atje and Jovanovic (1993) were among the first to add the stock market to cross country growth studies. According to them, stock market development affects economic growth. They took forty countries and used five year averaged data over the period 1970-1988. They concluded that the stock market had a significant impact on economic growth. Levine and Zervos (1996) investigated the relationship between liquidity measurement and economic growth. They selected sample for forty one countries for 17 years data (1976-1993) and total number of observation was 79. They measured stock market development along various dimensions: size, liquidity, international integration and volatility. More precisely their measures are aggregate stock market capitalization to GDP and the number of listed firms (size), domestic turnover and value traded (liquidity), integration with world capital markets, and the standard deviation of monthly stock returns (volatility). The results suggest a strong and statistically significant relationship between initial stock market development and subsequent economic growth. Including stock market liquidity, stock market capitalization and bank intermediation jointly as regressors yields a separate and significant influence on the rate of economic growth for each of them. This suggests that banks and stock markets play somewhat different roles in the process of economic development. They also found that the liquidity provided by stock markets had a strong positive impact on economic growth. Rousseau and Wachtel (2000) added a time dimension, and study the link between equity markets and growth for 47 countries between 1980-1995; in a dynamic panel setting. They concluded that the stock market play important role for economic growth.

Demirguc-Kunt and Levine (1996) also investigated in the link between stock market development and economic growth. They explained that the internationally integrated stock markets effect the allocation of capital, savings decisions, risk sharing

and the long run economic growth rate. Demirgüç-Kunt and Levine (1996) described various stock market indicators such as market capitalization ratio, the turnover ratios, number of listed companies, and the value traded ratio. They concluded that Japan, United States and United Kingdom are the three most developed stock market whereas Colombia, Venezuela, Nigeria, and Zimbabwe are the most underdeveloped stock markets.

Harris (1997) found that current investment significant but the stock market effect was much weaker than that suggested by Atje and Javonic (1993). He took forty nine countries and using data from 1980 to 1991. Trabelsi (2002) investigated cross country averaged data regressions for a sample of 69 developing countries during the period from 1960 to 1990. He found that the stock market positively affects on economic growth.

The related models by Bencivenga, Smith and Starr (1995 and 1996) posit that financial market conditions influence the production technology in use, its productivity, the savings rate and the composition of savings (that is primary versus secondary instruments). These influences arise from several hypothesised factors. Reductions in financial market transaction costs or increases in its liquidity favour the use of longer gestation production technologies because these technologies yield a higher internal rate of return, being more transactions intensive than shorter maturity case. Higher rate of growth would result if these are the more efficient production and the lower financial market transactions costs or higher liquidity would raise the productivity of all investment technologies, thereby again aiding growth. Finally, lower transaction costs or higher liquidity imply higher internal rate of return on all investments, higher savings rate and so higher growth rate.

Rousseau and Sylla (2005) found that stock market had a significant impact on business incorporations and investment. They focused instead on the early stages of economic growth in the U.S. (1790-1850). Arestis, Demetriades and Luintel (2001) investigated that the role of stock market in economic growth. They found that the impact of stock market on economic growth is positively.

Salvatore Capasso (2006) explained that the positive correlation between stock market development and economic growth is a well known empirical fact. Stock markets appear to emerge and develop only when economies reach a reasonable size, and the level of capital accumulation is high.

ECONOMETRIC METHODOLOGY

In this study, the methodology of vector autoregressive model (VAR) is applied to investigate the relationship between stock market and economic growth. A vector auto regression framework estimated as the first-difference of the logs is employed. In estimating time series model such as equation [1], it has since been well established that traditional OLS multiple regression analysis is not suitable since it requires the time series data to be stationary. When variable Y_t is stationary, that means it has a constant mean variance and co-variance which are independent of time. It will tend to revert to its mean value and vary around it within an approximately constant range. On the other hand, a non-stationary series has a different mean at different points in time, and has a variance that increases with sample size (Harris 1995). Unlike stationary time series, shocks to non-stationary series will be permanent and there will be no tendency for long-run mean-reversion (Ender 1995). In essence, the application of standard regression techniques to non-stationary data can yield spurious regressions with invalid inferences using t- and F-tests (Baltagi, 2005). For our purpose of investigating the relationship between stock market and economic growth of the Nepal, the use of growth rates should allow for permanent changes in the level of financial and economic development to be accounted for by the model, and ensure that the model captures the long-run relationship between the variables.

For this study, the application of standard OLS multiple regression analysis requires stationary data series. The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model was developed by Pesaran and Smith (1995) and demonstrated empirically in Pesaran and Pesaran (1997, 2005) and Pesaran et al (2006). The autoregressive distributed lag approach is applicable whether the underlying variables are

purely I(1), purely I(0) or integrated of the same order. This model particularly important for this study where a relatively large number of variables are employed, and integration of different orders likely. The ARDL models can be used to estimates the long run coefficients and that valid inferences may be made applying standard normal asymptotic theory. In addition, this ARDL model also reduces the problem of endogeneity because of the inclusion of dynamics, so long as the underlying model is free of serial correction (Pesaran and Shin, 1995).

This ARDL methodology has been employed in several recent studies, for example (Lewis, 1998 and 2004; Atkins and Coe, 2003; Coe and Serletis, 2006). In what follows therefore, the ARDL bounds testing approach is briefly described. The starting point for the model is a VAR (p), which can be expressed as

$$Y_t = \sum_{i=1}^p \theta_i Y_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad [1]$$

Where Y is an $N \times I$ matrix of demeaned endogenous variables, θ_i is an $N \times N$ matrix of coefficients, Y_{t-i} is the $N \times I$ matrix Y lagged of order i , and ε_t is a vector of white noise errors.

The data are transformed into annual average log growth rates. The intended effect of this transformation is to avoid the pitfall of picking up a short-run business cycle relationship between the finance and output variable and mistakenly inferring it as a long-run relationship. This is an important issue as differences are in principle the sum of permanent and transitory innovations. For questions of stock market and economic growth, long-run or permanent changes are really of interest, not transitory changes. For long-horizon differences of the sort used in this paper, the transitory component for each variable should be small, leaving only the permanent component. Therefore, the problem of picking up is business-cycle effects should be avoided, Chirinko, Fazzari, and Meyer (2004)¹.

1 Chirinko, Fazzari, and Meyer (2004) provide formal justification for the idea that long period data eliminates transitory noise.

Those familiar with the time-series literature on stock market and economic growth are probably well aware that another approach to capturing long-run relationships is to employ cointegration and vector-error-correction models (VECM). However, these will be misspecified if there is no cointegrating relationship. Meanwhile, a VECM corresponds to an infinite order VAR, while five-year average growth rates approximate long-run serial correlation in the data. Thus this research's approach is flexible and should account for any long-run relationship between stock market and economic growth.

The Bayesian VAR model with time-varying parameters used in this study is based on the model in Cogley and Sargent's 2001 *NBER Macroeconomics Annual* paper. The basic set up and presentation of the model follows (Cogley and Sargent, 2002) closely. Those interested in a deeper exposition are encouraged to read (Cogley and Sargent, 2002).

Suppose that we are interested in testing for the existing of a single long-run relationship between Y_t and X_t where X_t could be either a scalar or vector time series. Following Cogley and Sargent, the model is set up in state-space form with the following measurement equation

$$z_t = \alpha + \beta_t + \sum_{i=1}^p \theta_i z_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad [2]$$

where z_t is an $N \times I$ matrix of endogenous variables for $[Y_t \ X_t]'$, z_{t-1} is an $N \times K$ matrix of predetermined variables, θ_i is a $K \times I$ vector of time-varying coefficients, α is a vector of intercept terms $[\alpha_Y \ \alpha_X]'$, t is a linear time trend with $\beta = [\beta_Y \ \beta_X]'$ and ε_t is an $N \times I$ vector of error terms $[e_{Y,t} \ e_{X,t}]' \sim IN(0, Q)$, where Q (variance covariance matrix) is positive definite.

The ARDL methodology allows us to test for the existence of a single long-run relationship between Y and X . Thus, if our interest is in estimating and testing the long-run relationship between X and Y , this necessitates imposing the restriction $\Pi_{XY} = 0$. The implication then is that Y has no long-run effect on X or equivalently, that X is long-run forcing for

Y. That is, one unique cointegrating relationship exists between X and Y. However, Y could be Granger causal for X in short-run, with these effects reflected in the short-run response coefficients described by the matrices α_1 to α_p .

Now, we can write the vector error correction form of an ARDL (p,q) model in the variables Y and X as follows (Gujarti 2005, Baltagi, 2005):

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 T + \lambda Y_{t-1} + hX_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} q_{y,i} \Delta Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{q-1} q_{x,i} \Delta X_{t-i} + w \Delta X_t + u_t \quad [3]$$

Above equation [4] can be estimated by ordinary least squares, testing for the absent of a long-run relationship between Y_t and X_t by computing F statistic for the null hypothesis $\lambda = h = 0$. The alternative hypothesis $\lambda \neq 0$ and $h \neq 0$ imply that the long run relationship between Y_t and X_t can be described as follows:

$$Y_t = y_0 + y_1 t + y_2 x_t + v_t$$

The asymptotic distribution of the above mentioned F statistics is non-standard. Pesaran et al (2001, 2005) provided the appropriate critical value for varying number of regression (k) and the inclusion of different deterministic terms. There are two sets of critical values are provided. First, all the variables in the ARDL model are stationary by using first difference i. e. I(1) and the second that they are all nonstationary variables i. e. I(0). Therefore, if calculated F statistics for the above null hypothesis lies outside the relevant bounds, a conclusive decision can be made, whether the variables are I(1), I(0) or integrated of the same order. According to its decision, there is found that the long run relationship to exist among the set of variables and then the next stage is to estimate and make inferences about the coefficients of the long-run relationships (Baltagi, 2005).

Now, the following equation starts again with an aggregate production function of the form which is discussed earlier in Section above.

$$LY_t = a + bT + cLCAP_t + dLLAB_t + eLHCAP_t + LR\&D_t + gLFIN_t + \epsilon_t \quad [4]$$

Where, T is a linear time trend introduced as a proxy to capture technical progress and ϵ_t is a stochastic error term and other variables are discussed in above section. This study is focused two growth model, neo-classical and endogenous. In neo-classical model, technical progress is the main determinant factor of long run economic growth. Another endogenous growth model give emphasis physical capital (Rebelo, 1991), labour (Jones, 1995), human capital (Lucas, 1988) and R&D (Romer, 1990) to be positive relationship and significant engines of economic growth. In addition, endogenous finance-growth theory expects stock market and economic growth is positively relationship.

In addition, their high correlation and the overlap in their evolution suggests that separate estimation may not completely eliminate the effect of the other, and so any potential omitted variables biases may not be so severe. At the same time it allows the potentially differing characteristics of the estimated variables to be tested. This underlying problem probably highlights why most empirical studies in this area (Atje and Jovanovic, 1993, Harris, 1998)

The main objective of the objective is to find out the relationship between aggregate output and the factors of production especially the factors of finance. This entails estimating the error correction form of equation (5) and then implementing variables addition test for the lagged levels of all the variables. It is in effect a re-statement of estimation of equation in terms of our specific model. Given that the data employed in this study are all of yearly frequency, the maximum order lag chosen is 2. Thus, the relevant ARDL model in the equation is given below:

$$DLY_t = a_0 + a_1 T + \sum b_i DLY_{t-i} + \sum c_i DLCAP_{t-i} + \sum d_i DLLAB_{t-i} + \sum e_i DLHCAP_{t-i} + \sum g_i DLFIN_{t-i} + \lambda_1 L_{t-1} + \lambda_2 LCAP_{t-1} + \lambda_3 LLAB_{t-1} + \lambda_4 LHCAP_{t-1} + \lambda_5 R \& D_{t-1} + \lambda_6 LFIN_{t-1} + u_t \quad [5]$$

DLY = Aggregate Difference Log of the Gross Domestic Product

- DLCAP = Aggregate Difference Log of the Capital Stocks
- DLLAB = Aggregate Difference Log of the Labour
- DLHCAP = Aggregate Difference Log of the Human Capital
- DLR&D = Aggregate Difference Log of the Research and Development
- DLFIN = Aggregate Difference Log of the Stock market
- LY = Aggregate Log of the Gross Domestic Product
- LCAP = Aggregate Log of the Capital Stocks
- LLAB = Aggregate Log of the Labour
- LHCAP = Aggregate Log of the Human Capital
- LFIN = Aggregate Log of the Stock market development

It is an important to note that the factors X_i are long term effecting or only for the short term for Y; it is not possible to know. The values of X_i are excluded from equation [6]; the issue is examined subsequently below [also see Pesaran and Pesaran (1997), (2001), (2005)]. The test for the existence of a long-run relationship for the aggregate production is therefore of the null:

$H_0: \lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda_3 = \lambda_4 = \lambda_5 = \lambda_6 = 0$; against the alternative hypothesis;

$H_1: \lambda_1 \neq 0, \lambda_2 \neq 0, \lambda_3 \neq 0, \lambda_4 \neq 0, \lambda_5 \neq 0, \lambda_6 \neq 0$

Thus, the first step of this study is determined the existence of a long run relationship by using F test for the significance of lagged levels of the modeled variables in the error correction form of the underlying ARDL model. The second stage entails the direct estimation of the coefficients of the levels ARDL model using either the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) or the Schwarz Bayesian Criterion (SBC). The AIC tends to select higher order ARDL models and so yield smaller estimated standard errors and the other hand, SBC selects lower order models and so has the advantage of parsimony.

The Data and the Variables

This study employs a set of core data that have been previously collected and widely used in evaluating various growth models. In order to study the stock market and economic growth, there are two broad groups of variables employed in the aggregate-level ARDL modelling. Firstly, the variables relating stock market development, including for financial institutions and stock market development; and secondly, variables covering basic production function including output (gross domestic products), labor, capital and human resource. It is sourced from Ministry of Finance (Economic Survey), Nepal Rastra Bank (Financial Statistics), Annual reports of Nepal stock Exchange and Annual Report of Securities board of Nepal.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Econometric analysis is the most important for this study. It combines economic theory with statistics to analyze and test economic relationships. This study uses Vector Auto Regression (VAR) and Auto Regression Distribution Lag (ARDL) to identify the relationship between factors of productions and economic growth and then to find the causality relationship between stock market development and economic growth. Generally, economic variables are not stationary but econometric analysis is based on stationary data. Therefore, first, the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) tests are used to check whether each data series is integrated and has a unit root. The results of the integration tests are then pursued by co-integration tests based on a bi-variate VAR (bVAR) approach and ARDL model, to identify the causality impacts of stock market development on economic growth or whether a stable long run relationship between stock market development and growth exists. Based on the results, Granger causality tests are conducted to determine whether the current and lagged values of one variable affect another.

Unit root tests

The ADF test is the most popular methods of identification of stationary or non stationary variables. These tests were undertaken under the assumption of the existence of a unit root (H_0) and

a stationary variable in the alternative hypothesis (Ha). If the calculated statistics is greater than McKinnon's critical value, then the H₀ or that the variable is not stationary, is not rejected. If the variables are not stationary, these are transferred from non-stationary to stationary by difference methods.

According to the Dickey-Fuller (DF) model is as follows:

$$y_t = m + \alpha y_{t-1} + e_t \tag{6}$$

Where m is an intercept and *e_t* is a white noise. According to this model, the null hypothesis is a = 1 (non-stationary series) against the alternative hypothesis of a < 1 (stationary series). The error term in DF test might be serially correlated. The possibility of such serial correlation is eliminated in the following

Augmented Dickey-Fuller model:

$$\Delta y_t = \mu + \delta y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i \Delta y_{t-i} + e_t \tag{7}$$

where, d = a - 1

The null hypothesis of ADF is d = 0 against the alternative hypothesis of d < 0. Non-rejection of the null hypothesis implies that the time series is non-stationary whereas rejection means the time series is stationary. Phillips and Perron (PP) have suggested a nonparametric test as an alternative to the ADF test. Although the ADF test has been reported to be more reliable than the PP test, the problem of size distortion and low power of test make both these tests less useful (Maddala and Kim, 2003).

Table (1) below show that all the variables cannot reject the H₀ of I(1), that is, that all the variables of I(0) are non-stationary. Results of the ADF tests in Table (1) are given below that most of the variables are non-stationary because of the computed value of t is greater than critical value. Since the computed value of t is more negative than the critical value, we conclude that the first differenced of the variables are stationary; that is, it is I (1). However,

first differenced of the variables are turn out to be stationary. Based on the integration test results, co-integration tests are undertaken to verify whether there exists a long-run relationship between stock market development variables and economic growth variables.

Tables 1

The Order of Integration of Variables (1981 to 2012) Calculation of TS

Variables	Level test	First difference test
LGDP	-0.9687	-7.584
LCAP	-1.6197	-6.7029
LLAB	-3.3464	-4.4255
LHCAP	-3.219	-5.0503
LAT	0.418	-3.72
LMC	-0.7072	-5.1029
LNI	-0.7779	-5.1217

Note: All results generated using EVIEWS software student version.

The Existence of a Long-run Relationship

As discussed in econometric methodology section the main point is to find whether or not a long run relationship exists in the production function. This is the basic production function equation; that is the main objective of this equation is to investigate the long run relationship between gross domestic product and factors of productions without stock market development that is not finance augmented and then to investigate the relationship between gross domestic product and factors of production with stock market development. Therefore, this implies that the DLFIN components are omitted from equation [6] in this initial estimation of the ARDL model. Observations are used from period 1981 to 2009 throughout. This results are presented in table 2 is given below.

Table: 2 The Basic Production Function: Identifying the long-run estimates.

Estimating Dependent Variable: DLGDP by OLS, Observations: 1981 – 2012				
Regressor	Vector Error Correction Model		Variable Addition Test	
	Coefficient	t-ratio	Coefficient	t-ratio
DLGDP(-1)	0.17791	0.3605	0.4351	1.0886
DLGDP(-2)	0.1142	0.4321	0.4395	1.7233
DLCAP(-1)	0.5645	1.732	0.4035	0.8103
DLCAP(-2)	-0.3767	-1.4362	-0.0912	-0.3317
DLLAB(-1)	-0.1797	-0.6159	-0.4223	-2.5365
DLLAB(-2)	0.3133	1.072	-0.100	-0.4104
DLHCAP(-1)	0.1958	1.1014	1.2276	2.1669
DLHCAP(-2)	0.2878	1.4972	0.8734	2.330
LGDP(-1)	-	-	-1.0436	-2.8883
LCAP(-1)	-	-	0.4676	1.1057
LLAB(-1)	-	-	-0.3220	-1.2972
LHCAP(-1)	-	-	-1.0935	-1.5751
CONST	-0.00223	-0.2669		
Adj. R-squared = 0.6251, F-statistic = 4.3344, AIC = -3.3080			Adjusted R-squared = 0.5185, F-statistic = 2.6513, AIC = -4.1012	

Note: All results generated using EViews software student version.

Table 2 presented the identifying the long run estimation between output variable of gross domestic product and basic input variables. The discussion here to investigate between output and factors of production (input variables) by using ARDL model in addition test for the lagged levels of gross domestic product (LGDP), capital formation (LCAPA), labour (LLABA), and human capital (LHCAPA) in vector error correction model for output yields an F statistic of 2.6513. The critical values are 5.50 at 99 per cent 3.24 at 95 per cent and 2.45 at 90 per cent level of significance. The calculate value is less than table value at 99 per cent, 90 per cent and 95 per cent level of significance. Thus, at the 'traditional' significance level of at 99 per cent and 95 per cent the test generates an inconclusive result. It is only at the 90 per cent level of the significant that a stable long-run relationship appears to be suggested for the basic output equation that excludes the effects from stock market development.

As the same way in table 3, the study tests for the effect of financial development augmentation on the relationship between output and input variables with financial development variable, commencing with the stock markets development for the investigation of financial development and economic growth of Nepal. Previous paragraph tests explained about the test results with basic input variables i.e without financial. The next step, tests are run to examine whether augmenting with stock market variables. Table 3 summarizes the findings. The stock markets variables are classified into three; total market turnover, market capitalizations and NEPSE Indexes, those variables reflect the development of stock market of Nepal. Stock market turnover is the value of all stock market trades. It is employed to capture the trading activity and so the liquidity of capital markets more active stock markets will enhance stock market listing, portfolio diversification and the management of idiosyncratic risk. Market capitalization is the stock market value of all firms listed in the Nepal Stock Exchange. These variables indicate the activities of the Nepal stock market and it is expected that the activities variables show liquidity, risk diversification and portfolio management. A small and beginner stock market of Nepal would provide opportunities for portfolio diversification as well as incentives to the Nepalese investors.

Table 3: The Production Function and Financial Development: Identifying the long-run estimates with stock market development variables.

Estimating Dependent Variable: DLGDP by OLS, Observations: 1981 – 2012						
Regressor	With Market Capitalization		With NEPSE Index		With Annual Turnover	
	Coefficient	t-ratio	Coefficient	t-ratio	Coefficient	t-ratio
DLGDP(-1)	0.3013	0.8060	0.2602	0.6598	0.2973	0.7362
DLGDP(-2)	0.2589	1.0293	0.2630	1.0013	0.2565	0.9381
DLCAP(-1)	0.1568	0.3185	0.1827	0.3593	0.0936	0.1785
DLCAP(-2)	-0.2792	-1.0375	-0.2290	-0.8376	-0.2795	-0.9644
DLLAB(-1)	-0.2951	-1.7476	-0.3124	-1.8072	-0.2796	-1.4655
DLLAB(-2)	-0.0173	-0.0749	-0.0554	-0.2335	-0.0068	-0.0268
DLHCAP(-1)	1.2441	2.3619	1.2681	2.3100	1.0925	1.9414
DLHCAP(-2)	0.8683	2.4633	0.8836	2.4136	0.7890	2.1169
DLAT(-1)	-	-	-	-	0.01801	1.3961

DLAT(-2)	-	-	-	-	0.0073	0.5418
DLMC(-1)	0.0146	1.6908	-	-	-	-
DLMC(-2)	0.0035	0.4572	-	-	-	-
DLNI(-1)	-	-	0.0264	1.5971	-	-
DLNI(-2)	-	-	0.0081	0.5498	-	-
LGDP(-1)	-1.0118	-3.0781	-0.9686	-2.8119	-1.0507	-2.9518
LCAP(-1)	0.7589	1.8282	0.7508	1.7306	0.7376	1.6702
LLAB(-1)	-0.4006	-1.7506	-0.3877	-1.6332	-0.3486	1.3912
LHCAP(-1)	-1.1986	-1.8660	-1.2463	-1.8521	-1.0157	-1.4735
LAT(-1)	-	-	-	-	0.0292	1.6239
LMC(-1)	0.0214	1.9437	-	-	-	-
LNI(-1)	-	-	0.0371	1.7941	-	-
CONST	5.3062	2.3915	5.3059	2.2954	4.8281	2.0220
Adj. R-squared = 0.6042, F-statistic = 6.9510, AIC = -4.5173		Adjusted R-squared = 0.5703, F-statistic = 5.1958, AIC = -4.4349		Adjusted R-squared = 0.5350, F-statistic = 5.4704, AIC = -3.4235		

Note: All results generated using EViews software student version.

The study tests for the effect of stock market development table 3, it is show that including three variables; annual turnover, market capitalization and NEPSE indexes. The respective calculative F statistics are 5.4704, 6.9510 and 5.6958. These F statistics are greater than critical F statistics value, leads to a clear rejection of null hypothesis. These F statistics value of annual turnover, market capitalization and NEPSE indexes, which clearly rejects at 90 per cent, 95 per cent and even 99 percent level of significance. It is the evidence for the existence of a long-run relationship appears to be stronger.

Summary of findings with respect to the determination of the long run relations in the aggregate production function is given Table 4 below. The long run relationship without financial development variables is found weak evidence for the basic model. It is also found that is the long run relationship when the stock market variable is incorporated in the model.

According to above findings, it is confirmed that the long run relationship between stock market and economic growth for the output equation, the next

step involves testing whether the input variables, which include stock market development variables (annual turnover, market capitalizations and NEPSE Indexes) in our case, are long-run forcing for output. This issue is addressed by replicating the above variable addition test for the financial development (FIN) equations, with output as one of the Xi.

From the foregoing, it has been established that a long-run relationship exists for the finance augmented (banking development and stock market development) output equation but not for the stock market equations with LGDPA as an explanatory variable. This implies that the stock market augmentation is long-run forcing for output, but the reverse does not seem to hold. The study is now in a position to estimate the long-run coefficients of the finance-augmented aggregate production function and the associated error correction model.

Table 4: Summary of Findings

Model with variables	F-statistics	Significant long run relationship
Basic production function	2.6513	No
Stock Market Development		
With total turnover	5.4704	Yes
With market capitalization	6.9510	Yes, strong
With NEPSE Indexes	5.6958	Yes, strong

Note: All results generated using EViews software student version.

Estimating the Long-run Relationship

This study endeavors to investigate whether there is a relationship between stock market and economic growth in case of developing country Nepal. To test long-run robustness, ARDL model bounds testing technique is applied. To investigate long-run causal linkages and short-run dynamics, Engle-Granger causality and ARDL tests are applied respectively. That is, in addition to the basic model, estimates are provided for equation (9) below and their

using stock market variables as the relevant finance augmentations.

$$YA_t = a + bCAPA_t + cLABA_t + dHCAPA_t + eR\&DA_t + fFINA_t + \varepsilon_t \quad [9]$$

The result of the basic model is presented in Table 5 below. The ARDL (1,2,1,1,0) model is selected empirically, based on the Akaike Information Criterion. All the variables have the expected theoretical signs. A coefficient of human capital, HCAPA is 0.0129 obtained. The human capital is the most important factor for every nation but it appears very low and not statistically significant. It is also meaningful comparison could be made with any prior studies in term of size of the coefficient. However, it should be born in mind that labour variable also already incorporate some of the impact of human capital and it might also true due to the most of educated peoples are unemployment in the Nepal. In terms of prior findings, earlier studies point to a complex relationship between education and output or productivity and often suggest that education variables are not generally significant in economic growth for OECD countries, Rosenzweig (1996).

The study starts with the seminal paper of Lucas (1988) in this paper present about the human capital and economic growth. It showed that the economic growth depends on the growth rate of human capital and also depends on the time allocation of the individuals for acquiring skill i.e human capital. There are so many studies on human capital and economic growth so evidence from prior studies has been mixed. Benhabib and Spiegel (1994, 2005) found a negative and insignificant effect from human capital in a standard growth equation, but report a positive and significant effect on the growth of total factor productivity, while Barro (1998) found a positive and significant effect from male secondary and tertiary education but not from female, and not from primary education. Schultz (2003, 2004) observes that increasing expenditure on education may not be a significant growth factor.

While there is rather strong theoretical basis for a key role of human capital in economic growth (Romer 1986, 1989, 1990, Lucas 1988, Quah and Rauch

, 1990, Grossman and Helpman 1991), the empirical evidence is associated with contentious issues such as measurement of human capital and the structural form of the model in the regression analysis. On the other hand (Bassanini and Scarpeta, 2001; and Arnold, Bassanini and Scarpeta, 2007) found a positive and significant effect of human capital on growth for a cross section of OECD countries. This epitomizes one problem that has plagued empirical growth studies, especially of the cross-country type, i.e the diversity of explanatory variables, specific countries studied, time period covered, etc., which makes meaningful comparisons difficult. Comparable Nepal evidence is even scarcer. Many authors have analyzed the issue of human capital and economic growth in recent years.

The set of literature includes the works of Blankenau and Simpson (2004), Bovenberg and Jacobs (2003, 2005), Blankenau (2005), Brett and Weymark (2003) and of many others. Most of them deal with the effects of expenditures on education and growth. As a source of productivity, Haouas and Yagoubi (2005) examined openness and human capital as sources of productivity growth for MENA countries. Controlling for fixed effects as well as endogenously in the model, they found that while human capital significantly influence growth, it has no underlying effect on productivity growth. Park (2004) empirically investigated the growth implication of dispersion of population distribution in terms of educational attainment levels.

The labor is an also another important input variable in this study. The coefficient of labor is -0.0238. It is negative coefficient and statistically insignificant. Bearing in mind the fact that labor incorporates some human capital. Nepal is agricultural based country so more than 80 per cent people are involved in agricultural sectors. Lack of industries development many labors are unemployment. Therefore, Nepalese labors are unproductive and the long run coefficient is negative. The estimates would vary with the time period studied and the proxy employed, for example, hours worked instead of number of employees.

The econometric evidence for capital in table 7.6 the long run coefficient of capital is 0.0329. It is

positive but much lower than previous studies. This could be interpreted as evidence of finding that the physical capital is not supported for the Nepal.

These results indicate that for the Nepal, there is weak positive relationship between capital and economic growth. Comparable evidence on the role of capital in economic growth for the Nepal is rare. However, several studies by O'Mahony (1992) suggest a range of 0.058 to 0.66 while O'Mahony (1998) reports 0.45. Overall, the results suggest that endogenous growth is not supported by the data for the Nepal. On the other hand, the augmented version of the neoclassical model (Mankiw et al, 1992) appears to be supported, with human capital and R&D as the augmentations. Other studies also support our findings such as (Thakor, 2008; Thapa et al, 2007; Tarkka, 2006; Thapa, 2003) and among others.

Table 5: The Basic Production Function: ARDL and Long-run Estimates:

ARDL (1,2,1,1,0) Selected Based on Akaike Information Criterion.

A. Underlying ARDL Estimates:		
Dependent Variables: LGDP		
Sample: Annual data 1983-2009		
Regressor	Coefficient	t-ratio
(Constant)	1.647	1.927**
LGDP(-1)	0.2914	1.1414
LCAP	-0.3615	1.4911*
LCAP(-1)	0.4345	1.9134**
LCAP(-2)	-0.0497	-0.2351
LLAB	0.0573	0.3116
LLAB(-1)	-0.0742	-0.4188
LHCAP	0.0092	0.0427
Adjusted R-squared = 0.994, F-statistic = 447.828, AIC = -3.803		

Note: All results generated using EViews software student version.

** Significant at 5%

* Significant at 10%

B. Estimated Long-run Coefficients:

LCAP	0.0329
LLAB	-0.0238
LHCAP	0.0129
Constant	2.3243

Estimating the Long-run Relationship with Stock Market

The above table 5 presents the results for the basic model excluding financial development input variables. Next, the ARDL estimates of the finance-augmented output function are reported and discuss below.

Finance augmentation, commencing with the stock market variables in the ARDL model is selected by the data, based on the Akaike Information Criterion. The stock markets variables are classified into three; total market turnover, market capitalizations and NEPSE Indexes, those variables reflect the development of stock market of Nepal. Table 6 presents the long-run estimates when the value of stock market turnover is the finance augmentation employed based on Akaike Information Criterion selects an ARDL (1,1,1,0,0,0) model. Unlike in the previous two models, the LAT augmented model yields a significant human capital variable.

Thus, all the basic variables except labour variable are positive and statistically significant, and the estimated elasticities are broadly similar to earlier ones. With respect to the annual turnover variable the long run coefficient is 0.0257, it is positively but statistically insignificant. A percentage point increase in the size of the stock market would on average lead to a 0.0257 per cent increase in the level of output. Most of the results with annual market turnover are statically insignificant. Directly comparable evidence is rare, the magnitude of the stock market size coefficient (0.0257) is quite low than previous studies such as (Deidda and Fattouh, 2008; Carletti et al, 2007; Beck et al, 2007; Blankenau and Simpson, 2004; Bovenberg and Jacobs, 2003 and 2005; Blankenau, 2005; Brett and Weymark, 2003) and many others.

Table 6: The Finance-augmented Production Function: Stock Market Annual Turnover (AT) ARDL and Long-run Estimates:

ARDL (1,1,1,0,0,0) Selected Based on Akaike Information Criterion.

A. Underlying ARDL Estimates:		
Dependent Variables: LGDP		
Sample: Annual data 1982-2012		
Regressor	Coefficient	t-ratio
(Constant)	2.6806	0.7211
LGDP(-1)	0.2827	0.3485
LCAP	0.3866	0.8849
LCAP(-1)	0.1817	0.3935
LLAB	-0.4858	-0.7743
LLAB(-1)	-0.1173	-0.1739
LHCAP	0.1282	0.3929
LAT	0.0184	0.4557
Adjusted R-squared = 0.988, F-statistic = 43.7756, AIC = -4.1727		

Note: All results generated using EViews software student version.

B. Estimated Long-run Coefficients:

LCAP	0.7922
LLAB	-0.8407
LHCAP	0.1787
LAT	0.0257
Constant	3.7371

Table 7 shows the results when the stock market size variable is market capitalization (LMC), Akaike Information Criterion selects an ARDL (1,1,1,0,0,0) model. Again, the results indicate a positive and significant role for stock market size, although the inclusion of LMC seems to detract from the significant of LHCAP. There is no evidence of precedence in the use of this variables in the literature, thus comparable estimates cannot be cited here.

Table 7: The Finance-augmented Production Function: Stock Market, Market Capitalization (LMC) ARDL and Long-run Estimates:

ARDL (1,1,1,0,0,0) Selected Based on Akaike Information Criterion.

A. Underlying ARDL Estimates:		
Dependent Variables: LGDP		
Sample: Annual data 1982-2012		
Regressor	Coefficient	t-ratio
(Constant)	6.2181	1.4531*
LGDP(-1)	-0.3945	-0.4493
LCAP	0.095	0.2565
LCAP(-1)	0.7175	1.1808
LLAB	-0.3112	-0.6509
LLAB(-1)	-0.7611	-0.9509
LHCAP	-0.09472	-0.2859
LMC	0.1523	1.2809*
Adjusted R-squared = 0.988, F-statistic = 43.7756, AIC = -4.1727		

Note: All results generated using EViews software student version.

* Significant at 10%

B. Estimated Long-run Coefficients:

LCAP	0.5826
LLAB	-0.7689
LHCAP	-0.0679
LMC	0.1092
Constant	4.4590

Table 8 presents the estimates for the model augmented with the NEPSE Index (NI). The Akaike Information Criterion selects an ARDL (1,1,1, 0,0,0) model. All the variables are expected sing. As above analysis, all the variables, expect labour and human capital variables, are significant. The coefficient of NEPSE Index is positive and statistically significant. However, most of the results with NEPSE Indexes are statically insignificant. A percentage point increase in the size of stock market would on average lead to a 0.1032 increase in the level of output. The long run coefficient of the NEPSE Index is 0.1032 which is greater than the 0.05 the market capitalization coefficient reported in Van Nieuwerburgh et al (2001) for Belgium, 0.01

reported in Rousseau and Wachtel (2000) and 0.02 found by Levin and Zervos (1998) in cross-country contexts. Note that these studies employ different sets of conditioning variables.

The augmentation with NEPSE Index (LNI) yields results which indicate that there is a positive and significant role for the size of the stock market, after traditional economic inputs and 'engine of growth' have been accounted for. Further, the magnitude of the coefficient is plausible, in the light of related extant empirical findings.

Table 8: The Finance-augmented Production Function: Stock Market,

NEPSE Index (NI) ARDL and Long-run Estimates:

ARDL (1,1,1,0,0) Selected Based on Akaike Information Criterion.

A. Underlying ARDL Estimates:		
Dependent Variables: LGDP		
Sample: Annual data 1982-2007		
Regressor	Coefficient	t-ratio
(Constant)	4.008	0.9978
LGDP(-1)	-0.0102	-0.0115
LCAP	0.1284	0.3004
LCAP(-1)	0.5208	0.7582
LLAB	-0.3420	-0.6486
LLAB(-1)	-0.4422	0.5358
LHCAP	0.0289	0.0861
LNI	0.1043	0.7878
Adjusted R-squared = 0.9897, F-statistic = 48.1221, AIC = -4.2663		

Note: All results generated using EVIEWS software student version.

B. Estimated Long-run Coefficients:

LCAP	0.6426
LLAB	-0.7762
LHCAP	0.0286
LNI	0.1032
Constant	3.9675

Again, in line with finance-growth theory, the activity of the stock market is positively and significantly related to the level of aggregate output.

This finding has received much support in the extant literature. For example, Atje and Jovanovic (1993) found positive and significant effect of the value of stock market trades on both the level and growth of output, in a multi-country framework. Levine (1998b) also found evidence that value traded and turnover enter significantly into the growth model, using a multi-country framework. Furthermore, Harris (1997) also found some support for the role of stock market activity in growth, for a sample of developed countries. In terms of the size of the coefficient, comparisons are again difficult, but broad comparisons may be made. For example (Atje and Jovanovic, 1993; Levine and Zervos, 1998; Rousseau and Wachtel, 2000) which employ cross-country data, obtain stock market value traded coefficients of 0.04, 0.07, 0.05 respectively, compare to the 0.1032 obtained in this study. Furthermore, (Awad and Harb, 2005; Deidda and Fattouh, 2008; Levine and Schmukler, 2006) also found some support for the role of stock market activity in the economic growth. The discussion in chapter four elaborates on these prior findings.

Table 9: The (Finance-augmented) Production Function

Summary: Long-run Elasticity

Factor	Basic Model	LAT	LMC	LNI
LCAP	0.0329	0.7922	0.5826	0.6423
LLAB	-0.0238	-0.841	-0.769	-0.7762
LHCAP	0.0129	0.1787	-0.068	0.0286
LTL	-	-	-	-
LCBL	-	-	-	-
LAT	-	0.0257	-	-
LMC	-	-	0.109	-
LNI	-	-	-	0.1032

As above described this study has examined the relationship between inputs variables with and without financial development variables. The

causal effects among the considered variables were explored by means of ARDL vector error correction model tests. Table 9 exhibits a summary of the finding coefficients for various inputs regarding the long-run relationship for the finance-augmented output equation. Table 9 provides the following conclusions regarding to the results.

First, the basic inputs (physical capitals, labors, human capitals and research and developments) most of the variable display the positives sign except labor inputs and are all are statistically significant. Second, stock market variables (total market turnover, market capitalization and NEPSE Index) employed to financial development and activity all financial development variables exhibit positive and strongly positive sign and all are statistically significant. Third and finally, the role of the stock market in Nepalese economy is positive impact in the long run. According to the long run coefficients of financial development variables which are presented above table 9, the impact of stock market in Nepalese economy is positive in the long run.

Overall, above tables show that stock market in the long run has a positive and significant impact on growth. This finding is supported with the results reported by Rousseau and Wachtel (2000), Beck and Levine (2002), Awad and Harb (2005), Deidda and Fattouh (2008), Levine and Schmukler (2006).

CONCLUSION

This study explored the degree of relationship between stock market development and economic growth in Nepal. This paper has provided an overview of the emerging literature about the impact of stock market on economic growth and financial systems on economic performance of Nepal. There has been considerable discussion over a long period of time of the influence of stock market on economic performance. As above discussed above, the empirical analyses pointed consistently to an important role of stock market in economic performance.

The results provided the support of our study about the relationship between stock market and economic growth in the long run. Several reasons have been taken forward as possible explanations for these

findings of results. Nepal is a developing country and trying to improve the economic condition of Nepal, for the economic development capital is one of the most important factors. Thus, the paradox was resolved by highlighting the importance of the private sector in the allocation of resources by stock market developments. An innovative entrepreneurial sector continuously looking for the profitable projects, the financial sector could enhance growth substantially. The financial development affects economic growth mainly through an increase of investment efficiency; such a result also supports the hypothesis that the effects of financial institutions on economic growth are mainly transmitted through an increase in investment productivity. With respect to the stock market development for the long run economic growth, according to econometric analysis, stock market is importance for the long run economic growth.

When using ARDL model estimation with annual data over 1981 – 2009. Financial stock market is found to be positively related to economic growth. Thus, the stock market development has a positive impact on economic growth. Thus, the results were confirmed and this study concluded that overall stock market development matter for the growth. Above tables indicate, the coefficients of stock market for the long run are positives. Overall, the coefficients of stock market variables for the stock market development, suggest that it is so much quantitative as the qualitative effect of finance that is important in the relationship between stock market development and economic growth. However, underdeveloped financial development of Nepal, that is, it is required the amount of lending or funds raised in the financial markets as well as the more the qualitative improvements to investment efficiency

REFERENCES

- Aghion, P., P. Howitt, and D. Mayer-Foulkes (2005). "The Effect of Financial Development on Convergence: Theory and Evidence". *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 120, 173-222.
- Allen F. and D. Gale (1997). "Financial Market, Intermediaries and Intertemporal Smoothing". *Journal of Political Economy*, 105, 523-546.

- Arellano, M. and O. Bover (1995). "Another Look at the Instrumental-Variable Estimation of Error-Components Models". *Journal of Econometrics*, 68:pp.29-52.
- Arestis, A., P. Demetriades, and K. Luintel (2001). "Financial Development and Economic Growth: The Role of Stock Markets". *Journal of Money, Credit and Banking*, 33(1): pp.16-41.
- Atje, R. and B. Jovanovic (1993). "Stock Market and Development". *European Economic Review*, 37(2-3): pp.632-641.
- Atkins, F. J. and P. J. Coe (2002). "An ARDL Bounds Test of the Long-run Fisher Effect in the United States and Canada," *Journal of Macroeconomics* 24 (2): 255-266.
- Awad, A. M. and N. Harb (2005). "Financial Development and Economic Growth in Middle East". *Applied Financial Economics* 15 (15): 1041-51.
- Beck T., A. Demirgüç-Kunt, L. Laeven, and R. Levine (2004). "Finance, Firm Size and Growth". NBER Working paper
- Beck, T., A. Demirgüç-Kunt and R. Levine (2007). "Finance, Inequality and the Poor", *Journal of Economic Growth*, Springer, vol. 12(1). pp. 27-49.
- Ben Naceur, S. and S. Ghazouani (2003). "The Determinants of Stock Market Development in Some MENA Region Countries: A Panel Data Analysis". *Finance Research Working Paper*, October 2003.
- Berger, A. N. and N.G. Udell (2002). "Small Business Credit Availability and Relationship Lending: The Importance of Organisational Structure". *Economic Journal* 112, F32-F53.
- Bhandari, D. B. (2010). "Financial Institutions, the Role of Bank and Economic Growth". *Journal of Finance and Management*, Kathmandu Nepal vol 1 issue 1.
- Blankenau, W. F. (2005). "Public Schooling, College Subsidies and Growth", *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control*, Vol. 29, pp. 487-507.
- Blankenau, William F. and Nicole B. Simpson (2004). "Public Education Expenditures and Growth", *Journal of Development Economics*, 73(2): 583-605.
- Bludell, R. and S. Bond (1998). "Initial Conditions and Moment Restrictions in Dynamic Panel Data Models", *Journal of Econometrics*, 87: pp. 115-43.
- Boulila, G. and M. Trabelsi (2002). "Financial Development and Long Run Growth": Granger causality in a bivariate VAR structure, evidence from Tunisia 1962-1997, *ERF Working Papers*, September 2002.
- Bovenberg, A. L. and B. Jacobs, (2005). "Redistribution and Education Subsidies are Siamese Twins, *Journal of Public Economics*.
- Brett, C. and J. Weymark (2003). "Financing Education Using Optimal Redistributive Taxation" *Journal of Public Economics*, 87, 2549-2569.
- Cameron, L. (2007). "Investor Protection and the New Zealand Stock Market", Treasury Policy Perspectives Paper.
- Cameron, R. (1972). Banking and Economic Development, Some Lessons of History, New York
- Ciccone A., and E. Papaioannou, (2006) "Adjustment to Target Capital, Finance, and Growth", mimeo, Frankfurt.
- Coe, Patrick J. and Apostolos Serletis (2002). "Bounds Tests of the Theory of Purchasing Power Parity", *Journal of Banking & Finance*, Elsevier, vol. 26(1). 179-199.
- Cogley, Timothy and Thomas J. Sargent, (2002) "Evolving Post-World War II Inflation Dynamics" *NBER Macroeconomics Annual* 2001.
- Deidda, L. and B. Fattouh (2002). "Non-linearity Between Finance and Growth." *Economics Letters* 74 (3).
- Deidda, L., and B. Fattouh (2008). "Bank Financial Markets and Growth", *Journal of Financial Intermediation*.
- Demirgüç-Kunt, A., and V. Maksimovic (1998) "Law, Finance, and Firm Growth", *Journal of Finance*, 53, 2107-137.

- Diamond, D. (1984). "Financial Intermediation and Delegated Monitoring", *Review of Economic Studies*, 51, 393-414.
- Diamond, D.W. and P. Dybvig (1983). "Bank Runs, Deposit Insurance, and Liquidity", *Journal of Political Economy*.
- Fama Eugene F. (1980). "Banking in the Theory of Finance", *Journal of Monetary Economics*, U.S.A..
- Fisman, R., and I. Love (2003). "Trade Credit, Financial Intermediary Development, and Industry Growth", *Journal of Finance*, 58, 353-374.
- Fry, M.J. (1997) "In Favour of Financial Liberalization", *The Economic Journal* 107 (May): 754-770.
- Gavin, Michael and Racardo Hausmann (1996). "The Roots of Banking Crises: The Macroeconomic Context", *Inter-American Development Bank, Working Paper 318*, 1996.
- Goldsmith, R. (1969). Financial Structure and Development, (New Haven, Connecticut: Yale University Press).
- Granger, C.W.J. (1969). "Investigating Causal Relations by Econometric Models and Cross Spectral Methods", *Econometrica*, 37:pp. 424 – 438.
- Green, H. W. (2003). Econometric Analysis, 5th Ed. New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Greenwood, Jeremy and Bruce D. Smith (1997). "Financial Markets in Development, and the Development of Financial Markets" *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control*, January 1997, 21 (1). pp. 145-181.
- Hansson, P. and L. Jonung (1997). "Finance and Economic Growth", The Case of Sweden 1834-1991, *Working Paper Series in Economics and Finance* No. 176, Stockholm School of Economics.
- Harris, R. and R. Sollis (2003). Applied Time Series Modelling and Forecasting, John Wiley & Sons.
- Hellwig, M. (1991). "Banking, Financial Intermediation and Corporate Finance", in: A. Giovannini and C. Mayer (eds.). *European Financial Integration*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Holmström, B., and J. Tirole (1993). "Market Liquidity and Performance Monitoring", *Journal of Political Economy*.
- Jalil, Abdul and Ying Ma (2008). "Financial Development and Economic Growth: Time Series Evidence from Pakistan and China", *Journal of Economic Cooperation*, November (2008), 29(2). pp. 29-68
- Johansen, S., (1988). "Statistical Analysis of Cointegration Vectors", *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control* 12(2-3).
- Jung, Woo S. (1986). "Financial Development and Economic Growth: International Evidence." *Economic Development and Cultural Change*, January 1986, 34, pp. 333-344.
- Kar, M. and E.J. Pentecost (2000). "Financial Development and Economic Growth in Turkey: Further Evidence on the Causality Issue", *Economic Research Paper* No. 00/27.
- Kenichi, Ueda (2006). "Banks as Coordinators of Economic Growth", IMF Working Paper, No. 06/264.
- Kindleberger, C. P. (1987). "Financial Deregulation and Economic Performance: An Attempt to Relate European Financial History to Current LDC Issues," *Journal of Development Economics* 27(1/2) Special Issue, 339-353.
- King, R. G., and R. Levine (1993b). "Finance, Entrepreneurship, and Growth: Theory and Evidence, *Journal of Monetary Economics* 32: 513 – 542.
- King, R.G., and R. Levine (1993a). "Finance and Growth: Schumpeter Might be Right", *Quarterly Journal of Economics* 108 (3): 717-737.
- La Porta, R., F. López-de-Silanes, A. Shleifer, and R. Vishny (2002). "Government Ownership of Banks", *Journal of Finance*, 57, 265-302.
- Levine, R. (2000). "Bank-based or Market-based Financial Systems: Which is Better?" University of Minnesota: Department of Economics, mimeo, January.

- Levine, R. (2003). "More on Finance and Growth: More Finance, More Growth?" *Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis Journal Review*, Jul, 2003: p31-46.
- Levine, R. (2005). "Finance and Growth: Theory, Evidence, and Mechanisms", in P. Aghion and S. Durlauf, (eds). *The Handbook of Economic Growth* (Amsterdam: North Holland).
- Levine, R., Norman L., and T. Beck (2000b). "Finance and the Sources of Growth", *Journal of Financial Economics*, 58.
- Lucas, R.E. (1988). "On the Mechanics of Economic Development", *Journal of Monetary Economics*, July 1988: 22(1).
- Luintel, Kul and Mosahid Khan (1999). "A Quantitative Reassessment of the Finance-Growth Nexus: Evidence from a Multivariate VAR." *Journal of Development Economics*, December 1999, 60 (2). pp. 381-405.
- Mamuneas, T., Ketteni, E., A. Savvides and T. Stengos (2007). "Is the Financial Development and Economic Growth Relationship Nonlinear?" *Economic Bulletin*, vol. 15(14). pp. 1-12.
- McKinnon, R.I. (1973). Money and Capital in Economic Development, Brookings Institutions, Washington DC.
- Modigliani, F. and Miller, M. (1958); "The Cost of Capital, Corporation Finance and the Theory of Investment", *American Economic Review* 48 (3): 261-297.
- Nepal Rastra Bank (2009). *Macroeconomic Indicators of Nepal*, October 2009.
- Pesaran, Shin and R. Smith, (2001). "Bounds Testing Approaches to the Analysis of Level Relationships", *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 16: 289-326.
- Petersen, M. and R. Rajan (1994). "The Benefits of Lending Relationships: Evidence from Small Business Data", *Journal of Finance* 49, 3-37.
- Pyle, D.H. (1971). "On the Theory of Financial Intermediation", *Journal of Finance* 26, 737-747.
- Raghuram G. R. and L. Zingales (1998). "Financial Dependence and Growth", *American Economic Review*.
- Romer, P. (1989). "Capital Accumulation in the Theory of Long-Run Growth, in: Robert J. Barro, ed., *Modern Business Cycle Theory*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK.
- Rousseau, P. L. and P. Wachtel, (1998). "Financial Intermediation and Economic Performance: Historical Evidence From Five Industrialized Countries." *Journal of Money, Credit, and Banking*, 30 (4). pp. 657-678.
- Saint-Paul, G. (1992). "Technological Choice, Financial Markets and Economic Development" *European Economic Review*, Vol. 36, pp. 763-781
- Schumpeter, J. (1912). Theorie der wirtschaftlichen Entwicklung (Duncker and Humblot, Leipzig).
- Sherstha, M.K. and Bhandari, D. B. (2010) Financial Institutions and Financial Markets Asmita Publication, Kathmandu.
- Shaw, E.S. (1973). Financial Deepening and Economic Development, Oxford University Press, New York.
- Stiglitz, J. E., and A. Weiss (1981). "Credit Rationing in Markets with Imperfect Information" *American Economic Review*, 71, 393-410.
- Stulz, M. Rene (2000). "Does Financial Structure Matter for Economic Growth? A Corporate Finance Perspective", University of Ohio & World Bank.
- Thakor, A. V. (2008). "Issues in Financial Contracting and Financial System Architecture", *Journal of Financial Intermediation*, Elsevier, vol. 17(1). 1-15.